

Physically-Based Object-Oriented Databases for Geotechnical Engineering

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Abstract. The large number of published assessment procedures in geotechnical engineering, as well as the large and ever-growing number of field and experimental data sets makes it difficult to perform a full validation of a new procedure. Essentially demonstrating that the new procedure is superior to existing approaches across all existing observed evidence. To enable more effective validation, this paper presents a framework for linking experimental/field data with geotechnical assessment procedures using physically based object-orientated databases. A brief explanation of physically based object-oriented programming in engineering is presented, as well as a framework for the development of compatible databases. The database design covers several key aspects: behaviour based type checking, identification numbers for objects, object methods handle saving and loading exceptions, and the use of default attribute names. This philosophy is then applied to a specific problem of earthquake geotechnical engineering where publicly available centrifuge test results are compared with simplified methods for prediction of the build up of excess pore pressure and the triggering of seismically induced soil liquefaction.

Keywords: Object-oriented programming ·
Application programming interfaces · Soil liquefaction ·
Earthquake engineering · Centrifuge databases

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

At present, both experimental and numerical research produce a large amount of data that is often stored in a non-structured format or in a software specific format. For instance, in the case of laboratory experiments, researchers are increasingly worried with durability properties of materials, which need tests running for long periods and consequently producing much higher volumes of data that are often stored in spreadsheet files. Numerical simulations often produce an enormous amount of data that is often output into spreadsheets or a format that can only be opened by that specific software. Data storage and manipulation is a major aspect of conducting research and

needs an improved framework. Fortunately, all these analyses are producing data about physical objects, and therefore the framework should be orientated towards storing physical objects.

On the other hand, as highlighted by Millen et al. [1] it is generally very difficult to understand someone else's research, which hinders the possibility to independently validate it by comparing to other results. For that reason, in most cases the validation of existing hypothesis is performed only in a small group, where the datasets used for validation are often generated by the same people. The development of a shared framework for working with engineering research data, particularly in reference to how it is stored, should considerably increase the opportunities to independently validate research and improve communication around research findings.

1.2 Object-Oriented Programming in Engineering

Object-oriented programming (OOP) provides clear benefits for the manipulation of data about physical objects. Not only is it more intuitive, since the structured data can replicate the physical objects, but it also allows a reduction in the number of passed variables in an object-orientated framework, which has the potential to reduce input/output errors [1].

OOP allows the representation of physical or conceptual substances and its parameters as numerical objects. Instead of defining a set of independent variables covering the different parameters involved in the problem, as in spreadsheets or other functional programming languages, in OOP the data is structured in a more organized way, by linking parameters together by first defining the objects involved in the problem and then associating the involved parameters to each object. Since problem solving in the physical domain often involves parameters that are linked (e.g. beams, columns and floors are all linked by the building that they belong too), then explicitly developing these links using an OOP framework can greatly improve calculation workflow.

A key aspect of the workflow of engineering research is the saving and loading of data. The ability to directly save from, and load into, objects, saves time and effort, since researchers can not only download the previous work but they can then easily extend the objects giving them additional properties or parameters.

1.3 Convention Over Configuration

When people develop a set of calculations they often develop their own set of rules about how parameters should be named, how data should be loaded and how the calculations should be formatted. If the rules are not well established, then they often change between different projects, and even within the same project. The incompatibility of these seemingly trivial decisions can massively reduce the reusability of the calculations and increases the cognitive overhead of the user as they switch between these different sets of rules. The problem is compounded when multiple people are working on the same project and all have a different set of rules.

The development of a shared set of rules or conventions is a key aspect of effective collaboration and overcomes many issues of reusability of calculations as well as enables the automated bulk update or migration of databases. The philosophy of establishing conventions instead of allowing infinite configurability, known as ‘Convention over Configuration’ was established by David Heine with development of Ruby on Rails, to increase programmer productivity and reduce barriers to programming web applications [2]. The Ruby on Rails framework defines six principles: simplicity, reusability, expandability, testability, productivity and maintainability [2]. These six principles have been adopted in other software development frameworks such as Ember.js and Meteor, and provide a useful guide for the development of an engineering computation framework.

1.4 Database Design

Engineering data has an inherent hierarchal structure since it deals with physical objects that have attributes, and data is often associated with other data through spatial relationships and physical interactions. Therefore, engineering data favours structured relational databases compared to conventional tabulated or key-value pair-based storage. Unfortunately, hierarchal relational databases (e.g. SQL databases, h5 files) typically require a strict and explicit architecture for saving and loading data into structured objects. These architecture requirements can be a huge burden for research due to the large number of exceptions and unknowns that exist in research data, typically resulting in data being stored in an unstructured format. However, there are clear benefits in dealing with data about physical objects in an object orientated framework, and with establishing conventions for working with data.

To gain the benefits of saving and loading structured data, without being heavily burdened by excessive architecture requirements, a convention is proposed for saving and loading engineering data to and from structured json files. The convention offers the flexibility needed for engineering research, has minimal custom code overhead, yet is structured to enable collaboration and is easily updated or migrated. Furthermore, the json file format provides a human-readable, fully-web-compatible and language agnostic format. These final three advantages are hugely relevant for future developments. The human readable format means that humans can easily understand the calculation inputs and workflow and also allows efficient version control through line-based difference checking technologies such as git (<https://git-scm.com/>). The web-compatible format means that data can be shared between multiple servers, so data can be retrieved from one or multiple servers, as well as the calculations being performed on multiple servers or on a local machine. The language agnostic format enables multiple programming languages to manipulate data to make use of the full suite of existing implementations of engineering theory.

The database convention has four key aspects:

1. Behaviour based type checking
2. Identification numbers for objects
3. Object methods handle saving and loading exceptions
4. Default attribute names

Behaviour based type checking is a key aspect to providing a flexible workflow for research purposes. Behaviour based type checking means that the type of object is not determined by comparing the instance of an object against its class (typical in object-orientated programming), instead the type is determined by whether an object has particular attributes and what their values or behaviours are. In the proposed framework, the type checking for saving and loading is achieved by exposing a 'base_type' and 'type' attribute on each object. The base type is equivalent to the base class in a typical object-orientated inheritance system (or the Kingdom in the taxonomy of living organisms). In this case the base types are the types of physical objects represented in the problem (e.g. soil or foundation) and is the lowest level in the data structure. The 'type' is the key used to find the class of object that the data should be loaded as. This allows a dictionary of key-value pairs to be passed into a loading function, where the key is a conjugated string of the base_type and type, whereas the value is the class of the object that should be loaded for that data. This means that the same data can be loaded as different objects depending on the use case and research problem being studied. The use of behaviour-based type checking for the database does not exclude the use of class-based checking for other aspects of the source code, however, behaviour-based checking is preferred to maintain flexibility for unforeseen use cases. The inheritance of existing compatible objects is also encouraged to maintain behaviour unless explicitly changed. See an example on Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Example of behaviour based type checking.

The identification numbers provide the relationships between data in the same way as conventional structured databases (e.g. SQL). This covers relationships such as a soil profile object can have several layers of soil that would each be objects. The dependent relationship of one object to another can be saved in the json file by providing the id of that object as an attribute on the other object, and on loading the objects, they can be correctly related, either in a one-to-one, one-to-many or many-to-many relationship. All objects provide methods to export their attributes to json on saving, and to add the data

correctly to the objects on loading. This puts the onus on the object to be able to handle the incoming data, which can easily be extended to account for custom data attributes, rather than manipulating the data file or writing complex external loading functions. The use of default attributes for implemented physical objects, means that the same physical attributes have the same name amongst different languages, servers, users, etc. However, in the undesirable case when attributes are provided with different names then objects can be extended to provide both names for the attribute and on saving, the name would convert to the default option. A set of default names for base objects can be found at eng-tools (2018) [3].

Finally, time series based data is not suitable for a json file format due to the large number of tabulated values. A plain text comma-separated variable file provides a suitable alternative, where a physical location-based file naming system provides a suitable mechanism for identifying and loading appropriate files for comparison. At eng-tools (2018) there is systematic naming convention defined as four codes separated by hyphens, the first code provides the sensor type and orientation, followed by x position name, y position name and z-position name. Figure 2 presents a map of names for buildings on a layered soil profile, where the name ACCX-UB2-L2C-M corresponds to a horizontal accelerometer recording located under building B2 in the center of the second layer. The buildings are numbered inwards to outwards since the experimental campaigns tend to focus on a central building and add additional buildings either side. The soil layers are numbered from the top-down compared to bottom-up, such that two studies on the same site with different depths would have consistent numbering. For soil deposits with horizontal heterogeneity, the deposit can be represented as several profiles each with spatial coordinates, similar to a borehole.

Fig. 2. Sensor naming for multiple building analysis: convention for x and y coordinates.

1.5 Implementation

The database design has been implemented in the python package `sfsimodels` [4]. This package provides implementations of soil, soil profile, foundation, building and ground motion objects. The extension of these base models for specific problems can be found in the python package ‘`geofound`’ [5] for geotechnical problems related to building foundations, and in the `liquepy` package [6], for problems related to liquefaction.

The OOP philosophy is easily implemented if using Python programming language since there are a large number of standard libraries made available by users that enable, for instance, site response analysis, ground motion analysis, and unit analysis.

1.6 Existing Online Experimental and Field Data Repositories

The amount of opensource high-quality engineering data has rapidly increased in recent years due to key political initiatives (EU, US). There are numerous online repositories that allow the storage of experimental and field data, which can be used by researchers to compare with their own findings. There are some efforts to standardise these data repositories (e.g. [7, 8, 19]). Examples of these repositories in the area of earthquake engineering are:

- The European SERIES database promoted by the University of Patras, in Greece [7],
- The United States Design-Safe-CI database [8],
- The NGA2 strong ground motion database for shallow crustal earthquakes in active tectonic regimes promoted by the web-based Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center (PEER) [9]
- The European strong ground motion database [10]

2 Application of OOP to Specific Geotechnical Earthquake Engineering Research

2.1 Approach to a Specific Geotechnical Case

This section presents an example application where OOP was used to compare pore pressure build up during earthquake induced soil liquefaction obtained from centrifuge tests databases, with other simplified prediction methods. To ease the comparison with the centrifuge test database, the inputs of all cases (both numerical and centrifuge data) were standardized into json file format using the python package `sfsimodels`, where all the information regarding the ground profile, the soil parameters and the footing characteristics were stored. This information was organized in objects with the following variables:

- Soil profile inputs: name, ground water level, total soil profile height, layers, layer depth, layer height
- Soil inputs: relative density, dry unit weight, shear modulus, Poisson ratio, permeability, angle of shearing resistance, dilation angle, cohesion, minimum void ratio, maximum void ratio, porosity

- Foundation inputs: name, width, length, height, stiffness, mass, effective height, effective mass, ratio of horizontal seismic mass to vertical mass, structure effective period

The measured parameters resulting from both numerical and centrifuge data were also organized in a standard format where the name of each file was created as indicated above in Fig. 2.

This data was further analysed using python scripts that implement site response analysis and simplified liquefaction analysis in an object-orientated manner stored under version control on GitHub (www.github.com) and BitBucket (www.bitbucket.com) and shared among the research team involved in that particular objective. Since the team is using that same standardized format it is very easy to understand and use each other's code. In addition, this also reduces the possibility of mistakes since every researcher is using the same function to calculate the same problem, which can be first tested independently. Figure 3 illustrates the workflow of this application case.

Fig. 3. Workflow of the application case.

2.2 Pore Pressure Build up in Earthquake Induced Liquefaction

From the different approaches to predict liquefaction triggering the stress based method proposed initially by Seed et al. [11] and then updated further with time [12] is the most widely used. For this work, the pore pressure model developed for this method and proposed by Booker et al. [13] was used. This was implemented as described in Rios et al. [14], which involves the calculation of the ratio of the number of cycles by the number of cycles to liquefaction (N/N_L) through the CRR/CSR ratio (Eq. 1). CRR is the cyclic resistance ratio (assumed as the CSR_{15} obtained in undrained cyclic simple shear tests) and CSR is the cyclic stress ratio calculated by Eq. 2 where acc_{peaks} are obtained by a peak counting method from two times the input upward acceleration signal at the base. Note that in the simplified procedure from Boulanger and Idriss [12], the acceleration signal should be from the surface of the soil profile without the effects of pore pressure build up, which was not able to be obtained. On the other hand, the base input motion was determined as a suitable alternative as it was the only location that was not affected by pore pressure build up and was not affected by the interaction of the upward and downward waves. While σ_{v0} and σ'_{v0} stand for the initial total and effective stresses respectively, r_d is the shear stress reduction coefficient which depends on the depth and earthquake magnitude as proposed by Idriss [15].

$$\frac{N_L}{N} = \sum N_{ref} * \left(\frac{CRR}{CSR} \right)^{1/b} \quad (1)$$

$$CSR_{peaks} = |acc_{peaks}| * \frac{\sigma_{v0}}{\sigma'_{v0}} * r_d \quad (2)$$

To overcome issues with the use of the base motion, and uncertainties related to the shear stress reduction coefficient, a slightly different implementation of this method can be done, where CSR_{peaks} are the peaks of the CSR signal obtained by dividing the shear stresses calculated from equivalent linear site response analysis by the initial effective stress. The equivalent linear site response analysis was performed using the Python package pySRA v0.3.0 [16]. These two slightly different implementations of the method were called respectively SBM, for the original method, and Eq-Lin-SBM for the second.

These two simplified methods of estimating the pore pressure build up during earthquake induced liquefaction were compared with the dynamic centrifuge tests performed by Dashti et al. [17] which are publicly available on Design-Safe [8]. These test models comprise three layers as indicated in Fig. 4, where the thickness of each layer and the relative density of the middle loose sand layer were varied from test to test as explained in Dashti et al. [17]. In Fig. 4 the location of the sensors used in the present work are also indicated: in blue for the pore pressure sensors and in red for the acceleration sensor. The letters stand for the y-code as indicated in Fig. 2. The x-code for the pore pressure sensors is FFB2B1, which stands for free field between building 2 and building 1, while for the acceleration sensor the x-code is UB2, standing for under building 2.

Fig. 4. Model used in the centrifuge tests.

Figure 5 presents the results for a specific test (T3-30, where the loose layer has 3 m of thickness and 30% of relative density) in terms of the pore pressure ratio (r_u), defined by the ratio between the excess pore pressure and the initial effective vertical stress, for the 4 pore pressure sensors, together with the input acceleration signal.

Fig. 5. Centrifuge test results for test T3-30-Moderate Port Island 1995 Kobe [17].

In order to apply the simplified method described above, the CSR_{15} and the b value were needed. Taking the results of cyclic simple shear experiments presented by Karimi and Dashti [18] the CSR_{15} and the b value of Nevada Sand with 30% of relative density were computed, as illustrated in Fig. 6, where the following values were obtained: $CSR_{15} = 0.05$ and the b value 0.49. So, the two different approaches of the simplified method indicated above were computed with these values of CSR_{15} and b value.

Figure 7 shows the comparison between the described methods where it is clear that the simplified methods give a very good estimate of the time of liquefaction at around 10.5 s. In addition, both approaches (SBM and Eqlin-SBM) give very similar results indicating that for this case, the base motion issues and the uncertainties related to the shear stress reduction coefficient do not have a major effect.

Fig. 6. Cyclic simple shear tests for Nevada Sand with $D_r = 30\%$ [18].

Fig. 7. Comparison between pore pressure build up observed in centrifuge test T3-30 and simplified models.

3 Conclusions

This paper addresses the advantages of physically-based object-oriented databases highlighting that storing variables in a more structured way improves calculation speed, allows researchers to communicate better and reduces potential mistakes. The communication of research outputs is especially interesting as it allows more researchers to validate results independently and also improves collaborative work where a team is working on the same objective. This approach was implemented in a simple example of earthquake geotechnical engineering where results from previous researchers (from centrifuge tests) were compared with simplified methods for prediction of pore pressure during seismically induced soil liquefaction.

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